

Copper(II) Complexes of 3-*N*-Aryl Substitute Thioquinazolones

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Cu²⁺ complexes and their pyridine adducts of 3-phenyl/*p*-tolyl/*p*-methoxyphenyl/*p*-ethoxyphenyl/*p*-chlorophenyl/*p*-bromophenyl-quinazoline-2-thione-4-one (HL) are prepared. Elemental analysis, magnetic and spectral data show that the copper complexes without pyridine have square-planar structure and the pyridine adducts have tetragonal structure.

QUINAZOLINE-2-thione-4-one exhibits diverse coordinating behaviour¹ towards different metal ions. In some complexes, it is reported to behave as a monodentate ligand with sulphur or oxygen as the coordinating atom and in some other complexes as bidentate, coordinating through sulphur and tertiary nitrogen atoms. Even though a large number of related ligands are reported, the complexing behaviour of the title ligands are not much studied; only a few are reported²⁻⁵. In the present communication, we report Cu²⁺ complexes formed with several 3-*N*-arylquinazoline-2-thione-4-one (HL) and pyridine adducts. The 3-*N*-aryl substituents on quinazoline-2-thione-4-one used are: 3-phenyl (HPQT), 3-*p*-tolyl (HTQT), 3-*p*-methoxyphenyl (HMPQT), 3-*p*-ethoxyphenyl (HEPQT), *p*-chlorophenyl (HCPQT) and 3-*p*-bromophenyl (HBPQT).

X = H/CH₃/OCH₃/OC₂H₅/Cl/Br

Experimental

Analytical grade reagents and pure distilled solvents were used throughout the work.

p-Substituted-phenyl isothiocyanates were prepared as given in the literature⁶. These *p*-substituted-phenyl isothiocyanates and anthranilic acid in equimolar quantities were condensed in presence of glacial acetic acid to get the corresponding

ligands⁷. The ligands were found soluble in acetone, dioxane and partially soluble in methanol.

Copper complexes were prepared by mixing 0.1 *M* solution of cupric nitrate in distilled water and 0.1 *M* solution of the ligands in dioxane. The buff coloured precipitates immediately formed on mixing the solutions were digested on a water-bath for 30 min. The solids which separated were filtered, washed with hot water and acetone to remove excess metal ions and unreacted ligands, respectively. The complexes were found to be insoluble in common organic solvents except DMF.

The pyridine adducts of the above copper complexes were prepared by heating the latter in excess pyridine at 110° till a pasty mass was obtained. Excess pyridine present was pumped out at room temperature in vacuum, when the dry pyridine adducts were obtained. All the complexes were found to be insoluble in common organic solvents including DMF.

Nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldhal's⁸ method. Copper and sulphur were estimated gravimetrically by weighing as cupric oxide⁹ and barium sulphate¹⁰. The conductivity of the complexes which were soluble was determined using a Toshniwal conductivity bridge. Room temperature magnetic susceptibility was determined by Gouy method. The values are given in Table 1. Electronic spectra of the soluble complexes were recorded on a Beckman Du 7 high speed spectrophotometer in DMF. Ir spectra of the ligands and complexes were recorded on a Beckman spectrophotometer in the form of KBr pellets, at a range 4 000-200 cm⁻¹. Epr measurements were carried out on a Varian E9 spectrometer at room temperature and liquid N₂ temperature in polycrystalline state and in solution. Various epr parameters are given in Table 2.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA

Sl. no.	Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Molar conductance $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	Magnetic moment B.M.
		N	S	Cu		
1.	Cu(TQT) ₂	9.58 (9.83)	11.31 (11.27)	11.17 (11.15)	9.8	2.16
2.	Cu(MPQT) ₂	8.4 (8.9)	10.32 (10.17)	10.3 (10.1)	10.2	2.19
3.	Cu(EPQT) ₂	8.96 (8.52)	9.5 (9.73)	9.65 (9.66)	10.9	2.08
4.	Cu(CPQT) ₂	8.32 (8.77)	10.31 (10.02)	9.7 (9.9)	9.6	2.05
5.	Cu(BPQT) ₂	7.4 (7.7)	8.4 (8.8)	8.6 (8.7)	10.5	2.03
6.	Cu(PQT) ₂ 2py	11.48 (11.55)	8.6 (8.8)	8.78 (8.73)	—	2.05
7.	Cu(TQT) ₂ 2py	11.2 (11.12)	8.32 (8.47)	8.25 (8.41)	—	1.97
8.	Cu(MPQT) ₂	10.45 (10.67)	8.02 (8.13)	8.16 (8.06)	—	1.91
9.	Cu(EPQT) ₂ 2py	10.15 (10.3)	7.78 (7.85)	7.81 (7.79)	—	1.95
10.	Cu(CPQT) ₂ 2py	10.48 (10.55)	7.95 (8.04)	7.87 (7.97)	—	1.90
11.	Cu(BPQT) ₂ 2py	9.38 (9.49)	7.28 (7.23)	7.2 (7.17)	—	1.98

TABLE 2—EPR PARAMETERS

Sl. no.	Compd.	Polycrystalline state				Solution state					$\frac{G_{\text{average}}}{g_{\perp} - 2}$
		RT ^a		LN1 ^b		RT ^a	LN1 ^b		$\frac{g_{\parallel}}{A_{\parallel}} \times 10^{-4}$		
		g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	g_{iso}	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	A_{\parallel}		
1.	Cu(TQT) ₂	2.16	2.04	2.15	2.04	2.07	2.2	2.05	170.5	129	4.0
2.	Cu(MPQT) ₂	2.18	2.04	2.16	2.05	2.15	2.2	2.05	170	129	3.90
3.	Cu(EPQT) ₂	2.12	2.03	2.12	2.03	2.10	2.24	2.05	172.5	130	4.3
4.	Cu(CPQT) ₂	2.15	2.04	2.17	2.04	2.05	2.22	2.06	167	133	3.9
5.	Cu(BPQT) ₂	2.15	2.04	2.15	2.04	2.12	2.25	2.06	165	136	4.0
6.	Cu(PQT) ₂ 2py	2.25	2.07	2.32	2.08	2.10	2.21	2.05	165	134	4.0
7.	Cu(TQT) ₂ 2py	2.16	2.04	2.19	2.05	2.10	2.21	2.05	168	132	4.0
8.	Cu(MPQT) ₂ 2py	2.15	2.04	2.12	2.03	2.08	2.23	2.06	171.5	130	3.9
9.	Cu(EPQT) ₂ 2py	2.18	2.05	2.21	2.05	2.12	2.22	2.05	170.5	130	4.1
10.	Cu(CPQT) ₂ 2py	2.17	2.04	2.27	2.07	2.15	2.20	2.05	168	131	4.0
11.	Cu(BPQT) ₂ 2py	2.19	2.05	2.25	2.06	2.15	2.23	2.06	169	132	4.0

^aRT ≡ Room temperature, ^bLNT ≡ liquid N₂ temperature.

Results and Discussion

From the elemental analyses it was found that the non-pyridine copper complexes have 1 : 2 M-L stoichiometry and the pyridine adducts have 1 : 2 : 2 M-L-py stoichiometry. So the ligands behave as bidentate chelating agents. Molar conductances of the non-pyridine copper complexes were measured in DMF and have a very low value, suggesting the covalent nature of the complexes.

The values of the magnetic moment of the complexes were found to be 1.9-2.2 B.M., suggesting the presence of one unpaired electron. The excess over the value for one unpaired electron (1.73 B.M.) found for the complexes can be attributed to spin-orbit coupling^{11,12}. Pyridine molecules give rise to a six-coordinate complex.

It has been proved from the ir spectra that quinazoline-2-thione-4-one exists as thione in solid state, although it may change to thiol form in solution¹³. This is known to be the case in many such thiones¹⁴. In this case also the ir spectra show that the compounds exist as thiones. Since nitrogen atom at position 3 bears a substituent, there is only one NH group in the ligands. The band observed at 3100 cm⁻¹ is assigned to $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ (nitrogen at position 1) in the spectra of the ligands. It is not observed in the spectra of all the complexes. Hence, we conclude that the nitrogen atom at position 1 is taking part in coordination to metal ion. The band observed at about 1685 cm⁻¹ in all the ligands is considered to be due to $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$. It is observed with little change in the spectra of the complexes. So we conclude that the carbonyl

oxygen is not taking part in complex formation. In the spectra of the complexes, we observe two new bands at 690 (C—S) and 1610 cm^{-1} (C=N). The change from $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ to $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ shows that the mercapto form of the ligands binds itself to the metal. Hence, we assume that binding of the copper atom to the ligand is taking place through the nitrogen atom at position 1 and the negative sulphur of the thiol group. This is further supported by the far-ir studies which give evidence for M—N and M—S bonds. The bands due to these are observed at 480 and 310 cm^{-1} , respectively. In the case of pyridine adducts, we observe the band due to pyridine in addition to the bands observed for Cu^{2+} complexes. The complexes were quite stable at room temperature even though they contain a four-membered ring including the metal ion and sulphur. Such a stable system was reported earlier¹⁵.

The electronic spectra of the non-pyridine complexes were recorded in DMF. They show three weak bands at 555, 640 and 670 nm, which can be assigned to the transitions¹⁶, ${}^2E_g \leftarrow {}^2B_{1g}$, ${}^2B_{2g} \leftarrow {}^2B_{1g}$ and ${}^2A_{1g} \leftarrow {}^2B_{1g}$, on the assumption of a square-planar structure for these complexes. The pyridine adducts are insoluble even in DMF and hence their spectra in solution could not be studied.

Epr spectra of these complexes were recorded in solid state and in solution at room temperature and at liquid N_2 temperature. For non-pyridine complexes the DMF solution and for the pyridine adducts a mixture of pyridine and acetone solution, were used. Polycrystalline epr spectra of these complexes are of general shape¹⁷ from which the values of g_{\parallel} and g_{\perp} tensors were calculated. The spectra do not show any resolution at the g_{\perp} region. So it can be assumed that g_x and g_y are the same or nearly the same. We do not observe any $\Delta M_s = \pm 2$ transition at half-field at room temperature, thus ruling out any Cu—Cu interaction. Further, the G values, where $G = (g_{\parallel} - 2)/(g_{\perp} - 2)$, calculated for these complexes are four or nearly equal to four suggesting very low Cu—Cu interaction¹⁸.

From the room temperature solution spectra, $g_{\text{f.s.o}}$ and $A_{\text{f.s.o}}$ values were obtained. The $g_{\text{f.s.o}}$ values calculated from the room temperature polycrystalline as well as liquid N_2 temperature solution are in fair agreement with the above $g_{\text{f.s.o}}$ values. The liquid N_2 temperature solution spectra show four clear bands in the g_{\parallel} region, expected for Cu^{2+} complexes. Hyperfine splitting constants

$|A_{\parallel}|$ of copper calculated from the spectra are typical of square-planar copper complexes¹⁹. The fine structure in the g_{\perp} region may be due to the further splitting of the copper g_{\perp} band by nitrogen atoms. The superhyperfine splitting is found to be ≈ 13 G which is of the usual order due to nitrogen. The values of g_{\parallel} and g_{\perp} calculated at different conditions, are typical of copper(II) complexes with axial symmetry^{18,20}. In all the cases $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp}$, suggesting that the molecules are elongated tetragonal or square-planar with unpaired electron in the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital¹⁷, the ground state term being ${}^2B_{1g}$. The $g_{\parallel}/A_{\parallel}$ ratio is in the range of square-planar CuN_2S_2 complexes¹⁹.

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